

Field-Programmable Photonic Array for multipurpose microwave photonic applications

Daniel Pérez López
Universitat Politècnica de València,
iPronics
 Valencia, Spain
 dperez@iteam.upv.es

Aitor López Hernández
Universitat Politècnica de València
 Valencia, Spain
 ailoher@iteam.upv.es

Prometheus DasMahapatra
Universitat Politècnica de València,
iPronics
 Valencia, Spain
 prometheus@iteam.upv.es

José Capmany
Universitat Politècnica de València,
iPronics
 Valencia, Spain
 jcapmany@iteam.upv.es

Abstract— Software-defined Programmable Photonic ICs enable the dynamic configuration of their internal building blocks to realize the desired circuit. In this paper, we introduce basic and complex software algorithms to achieve multipurpose applications with a special focus on microwave photonics and report the experimental reconfigurations of the optical core for filtering and power splitting applications.

Keywords— programmable photonics, integrated optics, signal processing

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Field-Programmable Photonic Gate Arrays (FPPGAs)

Recent advances in Photonic Integrated Circuits (PIC) have focused on the realization of high density, low loss and potentially low power consumption components and circuits and to a lesser degree, on multi-purpose circuits. The primary emphasis has historically rested on the research, development and utilization of Application Specific Photonic Integrated Circuits (ASPICs). Designs such as these are based on optimization of parameters such as performance, optical power budget, electrical power consumption and footprint [1]. However, in regard to the development of ASPICs for low and moderate volumes, the multiple time-consuming cycles of custom design, fabrication, packaging, testing and their associated non-recurring costs involved in the development phase alone imply that they are far from being cost-effective for low to moderate volume fabrication[2].

The evolution of purely electronic circuits had undergone a phase as a result of which, majority of the realization of large volume demands of particular circuits were dealt with using Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), whereas low to moderate volume demands were tackled by the generic hardware platform of Field Programmable Gated Arrays (FPGAs). An extension of this analogy into the realms of PICs has resulted in the development of multipurpose programmable circuits and field programmable photonic arrays (FPPAs)[3-6] by virtue of which, a single generic PIC hardware made out of electro-optic actuators viz. tunable couplers and phase shifters along with high performance building blocks can cater to the demands of many, at a cost-effective rate and in the form of ready-to-use programmable solutions [3]. A fully software-controlled environment enables user-defined programming and reprogramming and permits the use of such chips across a multitude of platforms while performing as desired.

B. FPPGAs in Microwave Photonics

Multiple integrated microwave photonic (MWP) applications have been demonstrated relying on a basic set of electro-optical and optical components, [1]. Following the

Fig. 1. Field-Programmable Photonic Array, including a hexagonal reconfigurable optical core and several high-performance building blocks (HPBs).

FPPGA rationale, the integration of the most frequently used components in a common hardware platform enables the dynamic programming of multiple MWP applications. As an example, Fig. 1 illustrates a FPPA defined by a 112-Tunable Basic Unit (TBU) optical core and different High-Performance Building Blocks (HPB): optical sources, modulators, photodetectors, delay lines and filters suitable for a wide range of RF-photonics applications. All the elements are connected to the reconfigurable optical core in such a way that, not only do they produce the desired result, they also connect the internal and the external elements required for more complex functionalities. Thus, by tuning each 2x2 TBU or gate, one can route the *lightpath* and perform dynamic interconnections between the different elements describing a *circuit on demand*.

In this paper, we present basic algorithms enabling the use of FPPGAs for *self-characterization* and report experimental demonstrations of *circuit programming* based on presets.

II. WORKFLOW AND RESULTS

To enable dynamic operation, programmable photonics circuits employ a software framework that aggregates a wide variety of algorithms, methods or routines that are run by an electronic processor unit (PU). In general, this set of algorithms employ input arguments that come from the user settings, the data acquired by the optical power monitors or

Fig. 2. Programmable PIC simplified workflow including optional dynamic operation.

readout system, and/or data from analytical models [3]. Then, they decide on the configuration for the on-chip actuators in the circuit. In some cases, optimization tasks and other dynamic operations are required in order to compensate the operational drifts due to any tuning-related crosstalk of the programmed components and environmental changes, requiring the launch of recurrent or iterative procedures. A programmable PIC architecture can be reconfigured by means of its electronic control signals. These signals can be grouped together into the processor state or *actuation vector* $\mathbf{C} = (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots, c_N)$, where each c_i identifies a particular parameter of a given photonic actuator. For example, in the context of optical modulators systems, $c_i = \{0, V_{\pi/2}, V_{\pi}\}$ could define the voltage values for null, quadrature and maximum bias point of an internal modulator; $c_i = \{V_X, V_{\parallel}, V_K\}$ the voltage values for cross and bar operation of a 2×2 optical switch or TBU defined by a K coupling factor; $c_i = \{V_0, V_{\pi/2}, V_{\pi}, V_{3\pi/2}\}$ the voltage values required to achieve a given phase within an optical phase shifting element in a waveguide mesh arrangement. The common hardware platform would then implement different functionalities by changing the values of the components in its state vector, [3].

Figure 2 illustrates an example of a simplified workflow of a programmable PIC based on a waveguide-mesh arrangement. As an initial step, the *pre-evaluation* or approximate characterization of the subsystems is, in general, necessary for the correct performance or to provide a first evaluation of the circuit. After this task, which can be performed by the processor during its initialisation, the device

relies on the collected data to programme diverse functionalities. First, the subsystems implied in the operation must be enabled with the correct control signals. Next, the circuit topology and/or optical interconnections to be synthesized in the reconfigurable optical core must be chosen together with the high-level design parameters. For example, in the case of an optical filter synthesis based on cascaded ring resonators, the number of rings, coupling constants and differential phase applied to each ring must be computed. Once obtained, the required settings have to be programmed by properly feeding the \mathbf{C} data to the electronic circuitry enabling the actuation.

A. Self-characterization routine

Due to design and fabrication phase errors, the TBUs often present a random coupling factor in their passive state. Certain FPPGA algorithms need the knowledge of the approximated required driving for setting a TBU configuration into cross or bar state. The following algorithm and control scheme can be employed to compute the phase shifts necessary at each phase actuator to achieve the cross- and bar-states of each TBU. The architecture requires four optical monitoring points and two optical source points, located as specified in Fig. 3a. At each slot of time only one monitor and one optical source pair is employed. The waveguide mesh arrangement architecture is the one represented in Fig. 3a. It is composed by 36 TBUs (72 phase actuators) and 24 optical ports. The ratio between the number of optical monitoring points per optical ports, TBUs and phase actuators is 0.111, 0.055, 0.166, respectively. These figures show the reduced overhead of the proposed monitoring system location compared to the mesh size and the actuation system.

For the analytical validation of the scheme and the routine we simulate the waveguide mesh arrangement behavior with the analytical model developed in [7]. In this case, to increase the difficulty of the scenario, we assume a mean of 0.1 dB/TBU. For the random-coupling passive nature of the TBU we choose for each one, an initial phase deviation from a uniform distribution between 0 and 2π radians. The *self-characterization* algorithm does not know and does not have access to the passive phases, fixed during fabrication.

Fig. 3. (a) Waveguide mesh arrangement of 36 TBUs and the location of two optical sources and four optical power monitors for the *self-characterization* routine. (b) Phase error for learned cross and bar for each test, (c1) absolute power of the scattering matrix of the waveguide mesh arrangement at its passive random-phase state., (c2) absolute power of the scattering matrix of the waveguide mesh arrangement at its learned bar states.

Fig. 4. (a) Waveguide Schematic and configuration of the fabricated seven-cell feedforward/backward hexagonal waveguide mesh. Config1: Optical Ring Resonator of 6 primitive units, Config. 2: Second-order Coupled-Resonator Optical Waveguides of 6 primitive units, Config3: Two simultaneous optical delay lines working in parallel. (b) Measured normalized maximum optical power at the channels 11-23, 12-24 and 7-15 specified in (a) versus tuning steps of phase actuators. (c) Normalized spectral response measured for the different configurations: Configuration 1, Configuration 2 and Configuration 3.

However, it has non-simultaneous access to the readouts of source-monitor activation pairs. At each combination, it performs optical power minimization, through the actuation of the phase actuators that are in the vicinity but not in the targeted TBU paths and power maximization through the actuation in the targeted paths. We performed the test 100 times, imposing a fixed resolution in the phase sweeping of 0.03π rads. Under these conditions, the phase error for cross and bar state was for the 80% of the tests below 0.03π , as illustrated in Fig 3b. Although these figures are expected to improve with a finer tuning of the phases, the added noise from photodetectors, electrical and optical source variations and tuning-based crosstalk between phase actuators impose additional limitations. Each test performs the characterization of both phase actuators per TBU. Fig. 3c, illustrates one of the resulting scattering matrices at *passive* and *all-bar* states.

The procedure employed in this example can be summarized as followed:

procedure selfCharacterization

Require: Mesh definition and non-simultaneous access to optical readouts.

Require: *pathTable* including Paths to evaluate between Sources and detectors:

for *pathCounter* from 1 to *NPaths*

setOptimum(*NPaths*)

TBUs_in_path = selectPath(*pathTable*)

minimize_Neighbours(*TBUs_in_path*)

maximizePath(*TBUs_in_path*)

for *n* from 1 to *NTBUs_in_path*

[max, min] = findMaxMin (*TBU*_{*n*})

end for

end for

max, min elaborate the crossbar lookup-table including two inputs per actuator, 4 inputs per TBU.

Note that the procedure can be modified to obtain the functions of the coupling factor of each TBU versus driving electrical power.

B. Configuration stage: programming based on presets

Once performed the characterization either by a semi- or fully-automated process, the processing unit saves a look-up table with the functions mapping the driving values for setting the TBU in cross or bar. Then, it can start the configuration stage. In the following example, Fig. 4. shows how to configure the previous seven-cell hexagonal arrangement to programme three different circuits by using pre-set configurations. Note that in this case, C₁, C₄, A₃, A₇, B₁₁, B₁₂ are not included in the fabricated device.

In this experimental example, the software framework and the control subsystem are based on non-integrated driving subsystem based on a table-top multichannel current source, and an Optical Spectrum Analyser (OSA) as the optical monitor. As for the processor, we employ a standard personal computer and custom Python-based routines. The

communication interface is based on GPIB protocol. For the PIC, we employ the seven-cell structure reported in [4].

We saved the required configuration of three different circuit programming scenarios or circuits, referred in Fig. 4(a) as *Passive*, C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , respectively: an Optical Ring Resonator (ORR) with cavity length of 6-TBU, a second order coupled-resonator optical waveguides (CROW) with cavity length of 6-TBU and a simultaneous combination of two delay-line channels of 6- 5-TBUs, working in parallel. Each configuration is translated to an array C with the required electrical current value for each phase actuator in the waveguide mesh arrangement. While the cross-bar values were selected from the look-up table containing the pre-characterisation, the coupling factors of the TBU performing as tuneable couplers were selected and saved after measuring the critical coupling conditions or the preferred values.

In order to show the dynamic (re-)configuration of the waveguide mesh arrangement, we send the pre-set values of C_1 to the electrical drivers. In order to facilitate the illustration as well as to avoid a sudden injection of a current, all at once, the current increment was performed using steps of 5 mA per channel. Fig. 4b illustrates the peak power observed at the respective optical outputs between ports 11-23, 12-24 and 7-15, respectively. In the first re-configuration phase, we can appreciate the variation of the optical power of the three optical channels when the circuit is configured from its passive state to C_1 . The number of steps to configure is 41 and it is arising from the fact that least one of the channels needed to be configured from 0 to 205 mA. Here, the optical power has been normalised with respect to a straight waveguide of length 14 mm along with a 6.5 dB fibre-to-chip coupling loss.

As soon as the electrical sources reaches the targeted values of state C_1 , the spectrum is measured as illustrated in Fig. 4c. To obtain the spectrum, we performed a sweep with a tuneable laser and an OSA. We can appreciate that the targeted optical cavity ring resonator with extinction ratio > 23 dB is achieved.

The ensuing steps involve the electrical drivers reconfiguring the states from C_1 to C_2 . In this case, as depicted in Fig 4a, the targeted optical circuit is established by setting channels 12-24. The programmed circuit is a CROW with cavity lengths of 6-TBU. Again, Fig. 4b illustrates how the maximum optical power in the targeted channel increases till it reaches its optimum state. The proximity of the targeted C array to the previous configuration determines the number of steps required. The resulting spectrum is illustrated in Fig 4c. The critical coupling is achieved and results in an extinction ratio > 25 dB with a pass band ripple of approximately 3 dB (which can be further reduced by suitably adjusting TBUs H16 and H17 phase shifters).

Finally, the processor configures the electrical drivers to evolve from C_2 to C_3 . As depicted in Fig 4a, the third configuration emulates two different *lightpaths* or delay lines. In this case, channel 11-23 set is employed to implement a delay line of 5 TBU and channel 7-15 set implements a delay line of 6 TBU. The achieved spectrum is illustrated in Fig. 4c.

For the three configurations, we observe how the insertion loss of each circuit varies with the number of TBUs employed, as the loss associated with each TBU is in the order of 0.6 dB. In addition, the on-chip surface grating couplers have a loss of 6.5 ± 1 dB.

The reconfiguration time overall involves multiple considerations. The first is related to the thermo-optic actuators which require tens of microseconds. The second consideration comes from the electronic circuitry which requires 400 ms per step, including the tuning of 13 sources, sequentially. This limit arises from the fact that the setup employs a serial port protocol enabled via a USB connection in order to communicate to the electrical sources.

III. PROSPECTS IN PROGRAMMABLE MWP

Integrated MWP research can be fostered by the availability of a common hardware and software platform integrating the most commonly employed building blocks. The current paper demonstrates that by suitable programming it is possible to define a *circuit on demand* if all the necessary components are present in the circuit and a flexible routing is enabled. For complex MWP applications future research on co-integration of high-speed electronics with photonic integrated circuit is required, [1]. Moreover, improvements in the electronic circuitry and moving to PCB based driver and monitor arrays will negate speed and form-factor limitations as well as greatly improve the aspects of scalability of waveguide mesh arrangements.

A. Conclusions

In this paper, we have demonstrated, for the first time, dynamic reconfiguration in a FPPA based on presets. The demonstration is based on a combination of 1 linear path and 2 ring resonator-based filters so a total of 2 distinct functionalities across a combination of 3 input-output ports. As the reconfiguration here itself refers to the ability to use one common hardware for different functionalities, the absolute timing itself is not the highest priority as long as it is kept within a respectable limit. What is important however is the preservation of the functionality by ensuring that no significant overhead is incurred during the reconfiguration. The experiments carried out here have shown that we can use the circuit to perform multiple functionalities based on previously recorded pre-sets.

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